

Open & Transparent Research Practices

Case Study – Art and Design

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Introduction

Openness and transparency constitute a foundational principle for research integrity, as set out in the UK Concordat to Support Research Integrity. Openness can promote rigour, constructive scrutiny, accountability and can enable others to build on research. However, it can also bring challenges. Critically, what openness and transparency can and should mean varies across disciplines and fields of study. This is one of a series of case studies in a wide range of disciplines that illustrate these differences. The series is intended to enable researchers to see similarities and differences between fields, and to inform those supporting open research through, for example, training, policies or incentives. This case study is from the field of museum studies. It is based on a single interview with a researcher, and is therefore illustrative rather than representative.

Background

This case study explores openness and transparency in the field of museum studies. It is based on the experience of an Early Career Researcher working in a small team within a single discipline museum and working with an object-based collection dating from the 1600s. The Researcher is involved with museum sector research collaboration which includes industry partners, academics and museum professionals in national, local authority, and university museums. The Researcher's work explores relational materiality in the museum setting, with particular interest in how visitors and museum staff engage and relate to objects. Primary methods used in this research include observation, individual interviews and focus groups, archival research, and object-based research.

The research impacts on the working practices of the museum sector with the key means of dissemination achieved via written outputs such as books, journal articles, and conference papers, but also through less traditional means such as websites, social media such as blog posts, and practical resources created from the collaborative research. This includes toolkits, both physical and digital, written guides, and online exhibitions. The websites are interactive and very visual including images of objects, diagrams, and descriptions of research processes.

Relevance of openness & transparency

Transparency and openness are relevant in this field of museum studies as they show the value of the research, demonstrating how conclusions and outcomes have been reached. They provide evidence of how the research output has come into being and enable the dissemination to be broader than it would be if it were behind a paywall, allowing it to reach large audiences. The premise of museums is to be open and accessible to all so it follows that research should also be made open to a broader audience.

Because of the nature of museum collections, the primary source materials ought and should be open source. For example, all the non-published outputs such the guides to collection care and curation are made publicly accessible through the museum's website. In addition, the

methods and methodologies that led to the creation of these guides are also included online as part of the output.

Journal articles and conference papers that are published through traditional methods have been made openly available on the institutional repository subject to publisher restrictions. Books can be physically read via the museum library but are not currently subject to open access policies which means that publisher restrictions prohibit access to the resource. Contributions that the museum staff made to the REF are now in the public domain through the REF impact case study database, and 300-word statements for non-written outputs can be found on the REF submission website.

The terminology of transparency and openness are terms that the Researcher was less familiar with within their field. This is likely to be due to the fact that the activity of museums is about aiming towards being publicly open and accessible to all, it is in the nature of what museum practitioners do, the sharing of ideas and processes is all part of that activity.

Pros and cons of openness & transparency

The benefits of openness and transparency in the field are around the sharing of ideas. It means that research can easily be built upon without having to start afresh. Often funded projects will only take the work so far; enabling other groups or partnerships to build on what has been before promotes a forward trajectory.

There is a shift in museum theory and practice that sees the activity of museums become collaborative and discussion-based rather than simply imparting knowledge to the audiences. Traditionally, curators were the expert, and the knowledge that the curator had was the 'truth'. The audience was then educated in that truth, but there is now a greater understanding that peoples' lived experiences mean that they engage differently with collections and the stories behind them. They also bring their own knowledge to the activity of museum visiting, making a richer narrative. With this participatory approach, being open about your research and what you are doing, makes it easier for audiences to engage and feel a part of the activity of museums.

The difficulty of having high-level openness is the risk that other organisations can build on the research that has been done already and repurpose it as their own without credit as experienced by the interviewee. This is particularly frustrating when those organisations can attract significantly larger financial resources which enables them to develop outputs that are more in-depth, and with greater resource to promote the work. Openness means that this can occur internationally which is much more difficult to challenge. This is also a risk to an organisations' status in a particular field, and, as an early career researcher, it is a challenge to maintain intellectual property rights and build a reputation.

Wider context & trends

The publishing of methodologies differs between disciplines. For example, a science paper would reference the methods, results, and conclusions. However, museum studies papers are commonly written in a narrative style with papers focussing on the findings or outcomes of the research. They do not commonly describe the methods that led to the research, though work is being done to explore whether and how this might be useful. Open publishing and transparency in the humanities within which museum studies sit, is a topic of current, critical research in a number of areas and fields, which explore these good practices.

UKRI require that funding applications now include a data management plan which will ensure that data gathered for museum research will be discoverable and accessible, openly where the data are digitised and appropriately licensed by rights holders. Similarly, the new UKRI open access policy will dictate that long form outputs resulting from funded research will be made open access at the point of publication. This will have a significant impact of the research practices within the field of museum studies and humanities.

Museum studies research, supported through UKRI research funding, must meet their priorities for openness and transparency in terms of planning, execution, and dissemination. However, other funders in this field such as the Arts Council and Art Fund have different priorities. Whilst they increasingly require the outputs of the research to be publicly available to ensure maximum reach of the investment, this is driven by a desire for outputs and activities to be more accessible to a wider community. Equality, diversity, and inclusion are the key drivers in achieving this, with museums likely to have to be more innovative in their methods of dissemination to meet the needs of both academic and public audiences. But for these funders the transparency of the research process will be less of a priority.

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